

Speculation on Spin and Fermion/Boson Wavefunction Symmetry

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In (1), it is argued that the scattering of two identical particles may be described in terms of amplitudes/wavefunctions as: $f(\theta) + \exp(i \text{ phase}) f(180 - \theta)$, where the first summand represents particle a going to one point and b, to another and the second, the interchange of a and b. If one interchanges a second time, (1), argues that one must have $\exp(i \text{ phase}) \exp(i \text{ phase}) = 1$, so $\exp(i \text{ phase}) = \pm 1$. This leads to two wavefunction expressions: $|a\rangle|b\rangle + |b\rangle|a\rangle$ and $|a\rangle|b\rangle - |b\rangle|a\rangle$. (1) then makes the interesting statement that the first expression represents integer spin particles and the second, half-integer spin ones. The goal of this note is to speculate on why this should be the case. We ask: What does spin have to do with symmetry of interchange of identical particles?

We start with an unnormalized $p(e_i)$ from a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and note that: $\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$. This implies that (in terms of unnormalized probability which does not force particle number), an AND scenario of e_1 and e_2 is the same as e_1+e_2 itself. In other words, in the unnormalized case, the two particles e_1 and e_2 actually behave as if they have become one particle. The same idea carries over to the quantum free particle $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ cases. The question becomes: Can spin prevent two particles with identical states from being seen as one particle? Our argument is that for a photon it does not because electric and magnetic fields add, while frequency doubles, and so two identical photons superimposed may describe a single photon with double energy without upsetting the spin structure. Such is not the case for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ because we argue that it is based on the identity of a mass m_0 . Two particles have $2m_0$ and double the momentum, but the spin structure is based on the existence of the two masses m_0 and cannot be identical to a single $2m_0$ spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, we argue that $|a\rangle|b\rangle + |b\rangle|a\rangle$ cannot apply to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ because for a and b in the same state, one would not be able to distinguish that there are two particles. If one interchanges a and b and obtains a -1, then one essentially distinguishes that there are two particles (which do not act as a single new particle), we argue.

Maxwell-Boltzmann and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is based on the idea that for unnormalized probabilities (i.e. ignoring N) one has:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j) \quad ((1))$$

This implies that combining two particles with e_i, e_j is identical to having a single particle with e_i+e_j (if there is no normalization). This same idea seems to carry over to quantum free particles because:

$$\exp(-iE_1t)\exp(-iE_2t) = \exp(-i(E_1+E_2)t) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(i p_1x) \exp(i p_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((2))$$

In terms of energy and momentum, it is as if two combined particles behave as one with the sum of energy or momentum, at least in terms of probabilities, which we argue is what a wavefunction represents.

One may then ask: Why would spin possibly disrupt this scenario? Before trying to answer this question, we consider the idea of identical particles scattering as discussed in (1), because the answer to the question is directly related to the results of the discussion in (1).

Scattering of Identical Particles

In (1), the scattering of identical particles is considered. (1) states that an a and b (identical particles) may scatter, with particle a going to point 1 (described by theta) and particle b, to point 2 described by $f(180-\theta)$. Alternatively, one may interchange 1 and 2. In quantum mechanics, probability is linked to a wavefunction and so (1) suggests that one has:

$$f(\theta) + \exp(i\delta) f(180 - \theta) \quad ((3))$$

The second term represents the interchange of the first term (i.e. an interchange of a and b). Interchanging a second time, implies that

$$\exp(i\delta) \exp(i\delta) = 1 \quad (\text{according to (1)}) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(i\delta) = \pm 1 \quad ((4))$$

We argue this is equivalent to:

$$|a\rangle|b\rangle + |b\rangle|a\rangle \quad \text{or} \quad |a\rangle|b\rangle - |b\rangle|a\rangle \quad ((5))$$

We try to interpret the statement ((5)). We suggest that in the first case, interchanging a and b leads to no change in the wavefunction and this means that the two particles act as if they are one. One has no hint that there are two particles in terms of the overall wavefunction. Such is not the case for the second expression, meaning that a two particle identity must be retained. If a and b are identical for all quantum numbers, this leads to 0 for the wavefunction. We then ask: Is there any quantum property which is linked to the identity of a particle? We have argued in a previous note (2) that for a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle there is. In particular, we have suggested that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ arises because one has a rest mass m_0 . In other words, the presence of a specific mass yields spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, if there are two such masses, there must be two spin $\frac{1}{2}$ properties and not a single particle with $2m_0$ and spin $\frac{1}{2}$. We consider this in more detail.

Spin 1 and Spin $\frac{1}{2}$

In (2), we considered spin 1 and spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Spin 1 applies to a photon (as an example), and a photon has an electric and magnetic field which adds. Thus, if one has two identical photons at the same point, the electric and magnetic fields should add:

$$E+E = 2E \quad \text{and} \quad B+B = 2B \quad ((6a))$$

Now, E and B go as $\cos(-\omega t + px)$. If one has two photons and considers them as distinct (separated in space), then:

$$\text{Energy density} = 2 \left(.5 \epsilon_0 E E \cos(-\omega t + px) \cos(-\omega t + px) + .5 / \mu_0 B B \cos(-\omega t + px) \cos(-\omega t + px) \right) \quad ((6b))$$

Maxwell's equations, however, deal only with overall electric and magnetic fields, even in the case of no sources. Thus, considering the two photons at the same point strictly in terms of their electric fields, one must have the same overall energy as ((6b)). This implies using:

$$\omega \rightarrow 2\omega \text{ and } p \rightarrow 2p \quad ((7))$$

Energy density and momentum density are:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 4 E E \cos(-2\omega t + 2px) \cos(-2\omega t + 2px) + .5 / \mu_0 4 B B \cos(-2\omega t + 2px) \cos(-2\omega t + 2px) \quad ((8))$$

Integrating means multiplying dx of dt by 2 * .5 with 2 going to change the variable, so one has:

$$4 * .5 = 2 \quad ((9))$$

The same arguments hold for momentum density: $1/\mu_0 E \times B$ ((10))

In other words, the two photons act as a single photon with 2ω and $2p$. The point then is that photon spin arises from linearizing:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } \{ .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5 / \mu_0 B \cdot B \} + \text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 E \times B = 0 \quad ((11))$$

This leads to spin 1 because a Levi-Civita symbol ϵ_{ijk} (from the cross-product) arises. As a result, the same spin 1 arises whether one has a single photon with E, B, or the combined two photons with 2ω , $2p$, $2E$ and $2B$. As a result, the two photon system wavefunction should not change under an interchange of particles a and b.

In the case of spin $1/2$, matters seem to be different. We argued in (2) that spin $1/2$ arises because there is an a priori rest mass (representing energy) even with no momentum. In the photon case, there is no rest mass. Momentum is in one direction and the E and B fields lie in a plane perpendicular to this direction. With an a priori rest mass, all three axes need to be treated on the same footing even if momentum is only in one direction. Furthermore, because of the presence of rest mass, one cannot linearize $p \cdot p$ in:

$$-EE = p \cdot p \text{ cc} + \text{momo ccccc} \quad ((12))$$

We argue that one must have three spin matrices and they must "create" the orthogonality of $p \cdot p$ if one writes two linearized equations which combine to create ((12)), as Dirac did. The Pauli matrices allow for this. Actually, one has 4x4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices on the off-diagonals as Dirac showed. As a result, our argument is that an object with rest mass should

have all three spin matrices and there is two fold degeneracy (clockwise and counter clockwise rotation) about each axis. If one has two mo particles with the same quantum values, one cannot simply consider these as a single 2mo rest mass object which would then have spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Instead, one has a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ spinor for each particle. As a result, one must retain the identity of the two particles and the wavefunction must demonstrate this upon interchange of the particles, we argue. Thus, we suggest that:

$$|a>|b> - |b>|a> \quad ((13))$$

for spin $\frac{1}{2}$. This then suggests that one cannot have two spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles with the same quantum numbers. As a result, one cannot have a spin up particle scatter into a state with the same energy (and other quantum numbers) which is also spin up. This leads to a reaction balance equation of:

$$p(e1) (1-p(e3)) p(e2) (1-p(e4)) = p(e3) (1-p(e1)) p(e4) (1-p(e2)) \quad ((14))$$

We argue that spin is linked to the symmetry of a two particle wavefunction under interchange of the two identical particles.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) shows that one may have two wavefunction forms for two identical particles, namely: $|a>|b> + |b>|a>$ and $|a>|b> - |b>|a>$. We argue that the first shows no change under interchange of a and b and so it is as if one has lost sense of having two particles. The second, however, picks up a minus sign upon interchange, showing there are two particles and that their identity cannot disappear. (1) goes on to note that the first form is linked with integer spins (bosons) and the second, with half-integer spins (fermions).

In this note, we try to see why spin should affect the form of a two body identical particle wavefunction. We argue that in the photon case, two identical photons have their E and B values add, if they are at the same point, which means that the magnitudes (which are squared or $E \times B$ in the Poynting vector) pick up a factor of 4. The argument $\cos(-\omega t + px)\cos(-\omega t + px)$, however, becomes $\cos(-2\omega t + 2px)\cos(-2\omega t + 2px)$ and so one needs to multiply by 2^2 . The 2 is used to change the variable and 4^2 yields 2. Thus, one has twice the energy which is what the two photons would have if they were separated in space. The point we make is that two photons give the appearance of a photon with double the energy because electric and magnetic fields add. Thus, we suggest that $|a>|b> + |b>|a>$ applies to a photon.

In the case of spin $\frac{1}{2}$, we suggest that it is directly linked to the presence of a rest mass m_0 . In other words, $p \cdot p$ cannot be linearized in $-E^2 = p \cdot p c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ (without linearizing the whole equation). Thus, spin operators for a fully linearized form of the above must give rise to $p \cdot p$ and this means one must have s_x, s_y, s_z . The 2x2 Pauli matrices do the trick, but overall one requires Dirac's 4x4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices on the off-diagonals (of at least 3 4x4 matrices). We argue that m_0 creates spin $\frac{1}{2}$. If there are two identical particles with rest mass, one cannot consider these equivalent to one particle with double rest mass because spin $\frac{1}{2}$ arises from each mass. The identity of the two particles must be preserved and

we argue this means an interchange of two identical particles must have a signature showing this. We suggest that $|a\rangle|b\rangle - |b\rangle|a\rangle$ demonstrates this because a -1 appears. It seems that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is linked with an antisymmetric wavefunction on interchange of identical particles and spin 1 (photon) with a symmetric one. Given that the spatial portion cannot be antisymmetric, the spin portion must be and so for spin $\frac{1}{2}$, one cannot have two spin ups (or two spin downs) in the same state.

References

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